

SOCIAL MEDIA AS A CAMPAIGN TOOL AGAINST ONLINE GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The object of research: to explore the correlation between social media as a campaign tool against online gender-based violence (GBV) in South Africa.

The researchers investigated the following problem: Over the past decade, there have been several prominent incidents of harassment and stalking in South Africa. The issue of GBV against women in South Africa is prevalent in mainstream and online social media. Thus, women and girls are targeted in what is seemingly becoming a prolonged cycle of GBV in the country. The Cybercrimes Act 19 of 2020 was found to be a relevant legal framework in South Africa for responding to online GBV. Thus, the study was underpinned by social exchange and the spiral of silence theories.

Methods and Materials: In this non-empirical study, a systematic review was employed. Social media as a campaign tool against online gender-based violence (GBV) in South Africa was qualitatively studied. For the data collection process, the most recent repositories such as journal articles, books, reports, conference papers, dissertations and organizations' websites were gathered and systematically reviewed from July 2022 to November 2022. However, thematic analysis was used with due care to analyze data for the study. The NVivo software was used to identify common, repetitive and different themes.

The main results of the research are: As a result of the study's findings, there have been an increasing number of social media campaigns on sites such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter used by women all over the world to help combat the scourge of GBV. In this regard, women are using social media platforms to cry out for help and band together to fight a common enemy that violates their human rights and bodily integrity through social injustice.

The area of practical use of the research is for: This study is pivotal since it aimed at proposing intervention strategies to combat online GBV in South Africa. Most importantly, the outcome of this study will help in the development of more policy roadmaps for the successful combat of online GBV in South Africa and across the world. In a nutshell, the study recommends that law enforcement agencies, policymakers and civil society, among others, put in place additional frameworks to curb online GBV in South Africa.

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1. Introduction

Social media websites have become global, giving people a new way to interact with each other and communicate with the world [1]. Therefore, [2] posit that social media and social network tools, especially WhatsApp Messenger and Facebook, have become the dominant factor in today's digital world. The study conducted by [3] reveals that South Africa is regarded as the leading social network country in Africa. [4], define social media as "Web-based applications that allow people to create, share or exchange information, ideas and pictures or videos in virtual communication and networks. Among the most popular social media are Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and Instagram". As revealed by the [5], which is based in Pretoria, on the

whole, South Africa has made strides in uplifting women in the country. On the other hand, despite this progress, GBV remains unacceptably high. The high use of mobile phones has manifested in online GBV. Further, the embassy reveals that international declarations and local legislation show that GBV is a major obstacle to the achievement of equality, development and peace as violence impairs women's ability to enjoy basic human rights and freedoms as enshrined in various policies and conventions. Therefore, [6] believe that the rise in social media users has been accompanied by online misogyny – expression and behavior that reveals a deep disrespect for women. [7] posits that while GBV is not new, the technology dimension adds elements of searchability, persistence, replicability and scalability which facilitate aggressors' access to women they are targeting and can escalate and exacerbate harm. In this regard, [6] assert that misogynistic discourse perpetuates and normalizes unequal gender norms and this eventually leads to online GBV. The study conducted by [8] found that violence against women across Africa, and the globe, is pervasive, both in offline and online spaces. According to [6], narratives that perpetuate gender inequality in the media, including social media, are nothing new and occur worldwide. In this regard, [8] explains that online GBV is especially dangerous because many online spaces do not have enough rules and regulations to protect women from this type of violence, leading to perpetrators often not facing consequences for their harmful actions. Another group of persons susceptible to online violence is the LGBTIQ community [9]. [10] asserts that GBV is a profound and widespread problem in South Africa, impacting almost every aspect of life. As reported in South Africa's [11], South Africa holds the shameful distinction of being one of the most unsafe places in the world to be a woman. [10] further discovered that GBV (which disproportionately affects women and girls) is systemic and deeply entrenched in institutions, cultures and traditions in South Africa.

[12] explain that the term GBV also refers to the diverse ways in which criminal, civil or otherwise harmful sexually aggressive and harassing behaviors are being perpetrated with the aid or use of digital communication technologies. In this regard, [13] describe online GBV as an action carried out by one or more people that endangers others because of their sexual or gender identity or by enforcing dangerous gender norms. This action is performed using the internet and/or cellular technology. In this regard, the [11] defines online violence as any act of GBV against a woman that is committed, assisted, or aggravated in part or fully by the use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT), such as mobile phones and smartphones, the internet, social media platforms or email, against a woman because she is a woman, or affects women disproportionately. According to [6], the acts of online GBV include stalking, hacking and cyberbullying of women by men. In addition, [8] states that some common forms of online GBV include cyberbullying (bullying with the use of digital technologies), doxing (revealing or publishing private information about a person online), cyberstalking (the use of the internet to stalk or harass another person), non-consensual pornography (distribution of sexually graphic images without consent) and trolling (deliberately upsetting other people by posting inflammatory content). The study conducted by [14] found that young women and girls appear to experience higher rates of online sexual violence than any other group. Thus, [15] indicate that social media is an effective tool for communication and coordination among activists. In addition to this, [6] emphasize that its massive reach, and its informal and dynamic nature, offer opportunities for innovation in building a safer world for women and girls both online and offline.

This study is pivotal since it aimed at proposing intervention strategies to combat online GBV in South Africa. Most importantly, the outcome of this study will help in the development of more policy roadmaps for the successful combat of online GBV in South Africa and across the world. The paper will outline the statement of the research problem, and research questions, and the theoretical framework and legal framework will be provided. Methodology, findings and discussions will then be presented, followed by the conclusion and recommendations.

1. 1. The object of research

The object of this research is to systematically explore the correlation between social media as a campaign tool against online gender-based violence (GBV) in South Africa.

1. 2. Problem description

[9] indicates that over the past decade, there have been several prominent incidents of harassment and stalking in South Africa. [16] concur that the issue of GBV against women in South Africa is prevalent in mainstream and online social media. Thus, women and girls are targeted in what is seemingly becoming a prolonged cycle of GBV in the country. As indicated by [17], those women and girls are particularly affected because of their vulnerable social and economic positions. [18] maintains that women and LGBTIQ people routinely experience online harassment in South Africa. Although there is a lack of data on the extent and prevalence of online GBV compared to GBV in the physical world, the information available points to the possibility that it could spiral out of control if not addressed seriously. [8] asserts that online GBV isolates women and reaffirms patriarchal norms that tend to silence them and limit their freedoms. This in turn extends gender inequality into all spaces, leaving women with few places to turn to for support, virtually or in reality.

The research questions of this study were as follows:

- How do South Africans use social media platforms?
- What are the causes of online GBV in South Africa?
- What are the solutions to curb online GBV in South Africa?

The next section outline the theoretical framework relevant the paper. The social exchange and Spiral of silence theories are discussed below.

1. 2. 1. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical frameworks for this paper were social exchange and spiral of silence theories. The theories are outlined below:

Social exchange theory (SET) as a theoretical lens of the study.

Since the study was on social media as a campaign tool against online GBV in South Africa, SET was adopted and deemed relevant. The primary reason for adopting this theory was to explain the communication exchange of people, how people build relationships and how these relationships sometimes lead to online GBV. SET is one of the most influential conceptual paradigms concerning the behavior of individuals and the ability of people to change one another's behavior through variations of their behavior control [19]. It is crucial to note that social network users determine their socialization through the way they exchange messages, and this shows that even online GBV activities are fuelled by the social exchange that takes place online. [19] also point out that among many basic tenets of SET is that relationships evolve into trusting, loyal and mutual commitments and rules of exchange. This statement is key to this study because if social media users develop trust, loyalty and mutual commitments and rules of exchange, there could be a solution to the online GBV problem in South Africa.

Spiral of silence theory as the lens of the study.

In the context of online GBV in South Africa, the spiral of silence was also used as a theoretical lens to investigate the root of online GBV in South Africa. In this study, this theory was used to explain why individuals sometimes feel unable to speak up when abused online. According to [20], the spiral of silence is a collective phenomenon which involves individuals relating their perspectives to those of others.

Freedom of expression and access to information are key enabling rights to a range of human rights. [9] postulates that online GBV causes a spiral of silence, and this prevents women and girls from fully exercising these rights online, especially when they are abused. [9] is concerned that as a consequence, victims and survivors of online GBV may be reluctant to seek assistance, or they are silenced and isolated by shame. [9] further indicates that removing violence against women from digital and online platforms has the net effect of promoting and strengthening freedom of expression as it creates an environment that allows more individuals, especially sections of society who face discrimination in other public spaces, to participate in these media.

1. 2. 2. Legal framework to respond to online GBV in South Africa

When the internet opened the door for communities and individuals to connect, discrimination, hate speech and virtual human rights violations became uninvited guests [8].

The Cybercrimes Act, 2020 (Act 19 of 2020) was found in this study to be a relevant legal framework to respond to online GBV in South Africa. The main reason the Cybercrimes Act, 2020 was the relevant legal framework for this study is that it stipulates penalties for those who are involved in online criminal activities such as GBV. This Act was passed by the President of the Republic of South Africa, Mr Cyril Ramaphosa to create offences that have a bearing on cybercrime; to criminalize the disclosure of data messages which are harmful and provide for interim protection orders; to further regulate jurisdiction in respect of cybercrimes; to further regulate the powers to investigate cybercrimes and to further regulate aspects relating to mutual assistance in respect of the investigation of cybercrimes, among others. With special reference to this Act, the South African government, together with social media researchers and developers, need to implement social media policies that firmly punish instigators who use social media to commit online GBV against women and the LGBTQ+ community.

1. 2. 3. Review of related literature

Usage of social media platforms by South Africans.

The use of social media in South Africa has continued to grow, specifically regarding the number of users and the intensity of use by current social media members [21]. In relation to the previous statement, the study conducted by [6] reveals that most South Africans use social media platforms such as Twitter, and these powerful platforms influence public opinion, but also promote and legitimise acts of GBV such as intolerance, distrust and hate. According to [8], feminists in (South) Africa have used social media to rally against GBV which includes everything from harassment to doxing – a type of abuse that reveals a person’s private information. [6] explain that South Africans use social media platforms to mobilize the public and build solidarity. As explained by the [22], people are embracing social media to communicate in ways that could never have been imagined just a few years ago.

[23] discovered that social media is by far the most common venue cited for harassment and GBV. According to the [18], in South Africa, research suggests that incidences of GBV occur primarily on platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and WhatsApp. [8] points out that because of social media, a woman can be harassed by thousands of people she does not even know, and those who would normally not have access to her. This is an everyday occurrence for many outspoken women on social media.

An online survey of 90 LGBTIQ young adults aged between 18 and 34 from South Africa reveals a high incidence of exclusion, outing and harassment, covering a wide variety of types, duration and experienced severity, taking place through text messaging and social media sites such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter [18]. Online GBV against women also occurs in workplaces. For example, online GBV against women journalists is an increasingly threatening form of silencing women in the media, which poses a clear threat not only to their safety and well-being but also to the diversity of voices in the media and freedom of expression and access to information.

Root causes of online GBV in South Africa.

[9] reveals that patriarchy causes online GBV and emphasizes that women who establish cyberfriendships or relationships may become victims of online GBV. Furthermore, [9] reports that a lack of support for the victims/survivors of online violence against women causes GBV to spread. According to [7], another cause of online GBV is the lack of access to other kinds of public spaces for the exchange of information and organizing. The Association stresses that this makes it essential to respond to the specific risks they face online. The prominence of Facebook and chat platforms such as WhatsApp as platforms where online GBV often occurs in South Africa may be because Facebook does not require the verification of users on signup (such as providing a phone number), making it easier for people to hide their identity while using the platform [16]. As long as the information is shared on the internet, a person is vulnerable to harassment, discrimination and violence online. Women and girls are often particularly targeted, especially if they are politically outspoken, African black, identify as LGBTQ+, or have a disability [8].

As [13] see it, among the many causes of online GBV is that there is a lack of public awareness of the GBV issue. [8] maintains that existing legal frameworks are insufficient to deal with online GBV and there is very little social support. As revealed by [1], the reason online GBV continues to take place is that some social networking site users are not aware of what exactly can be considered harassment or illegal activity. Many people do not even bother reporting the negativity they come across on the internet for fear of the trouble it may cause them or the thought that no one may even read it anyway.

According to [24], online GBV is informed by the connection or relationship between the victim/survivor and the perpetrator. This relationship may be personal or impersonal or institutional, in which public figures or state entities commit GBV through technology to further an ideological agenda or enforce a law. Further, [24] point out that every victim/survivor is impacted in some way by their experience. Those impacts can include significant harm to their physical and mental health, social status and economic opportunities and, in some cases, have led to death.

According to [7], the acts of online GBV are often an extension of existing GBV such as domestic violence, stalking and sexual harassment, or targeting the victim based on her gender or sexuality. Further, the Association posits that infringement of privacy such as accessing, using, manipulating and/or disseminating private data without consent (by cracking personal accounts, stealing passwords, using/stealing identities, using another person's computer to access a user's accounts while it is logged in, etc.) constitute online GBV.

The study conducted by [25] argues that GBV is also pervasive in South Africa, where cultural norms and gender-based customs and traditions condone and reinforce abusive practices. Participants in the study conducted by [26] repeatedly commented on the fact that violence is almost seen as 'normal' in their communities, as it is so common. Further, participants noted that South Africa is a very violent society, where GBV is rife. In addition, the above authors emphasize that patriarchal and sexist views legitimize violence to ensure the dominance and superiority of men.

Solutions to prevent online GBV in South Africa.

The availability of a social network also increases women's autonomy and their ability to seek support and assistance related to online GBV [9]. [9] contends that outreach programmes can end isolation and remove the stigma of online GBV.

Most importantly, [27] states that efforts to end violence and exploitation must include strategies for changing the environments in which violence and exploitation occur. Further, he emphasises that while violence prevention efforts need to focus on perpetrator behaviour and the risk factors that render victims vulnerable, they must also incorporate methodologies that can foster more comprehensive environmental change.

As expressed by [6], social media can change actions that drive GBV. They strongly believe that combining social media campaigns with in-person interventions delivers promising results. They give the example of the Must Bol campaign in India. The campaign takes place in online and offline spaces for youth to engage on topics relating to GBV. [8] mentions that staying informed on the different types of online GBV is essential for taking action, and people can do this by following and supporting social media accounts advocating for the end of this type of violence. According to the [28], as social and behavior change communication campaigns include more social media components, data from Twitter or other social media platforms may help understand access, use and reaction to GBV campaigns.

There is a need to educate social media users about the benefits and disadvantages of this media [29]. In this regard, [6] believe that social media users must realise that *how* they talk about online GBV is crucial in addressing it, and *where* they speak about it matters too. According to the [18], social media providers need to take more responsibility in ensuring a safe internet where there is no place for online GBV, developing practical measures to help women and address online GBV, for example by taking down content where violations have been reported. They must also make their reporting mechanisms known and user-friendly for those who want to report online GBV occurrences. [24] also indicate that there are a variety of help-seeking or coping behaviours that a victim/survivor can take that include, but are not limited to, reporting their experience and seeking help from their social networks.

[11] states that social media owners should intervene and immediately take firm action, including moderating comments, publicly condemning perpetrators, reporting them to authorities, or banning such users. Furthermore, owners should adopt zero-tolerance policies for cyber violence.

According to [9], the increased prevalence of online GBV, the lack of effective measures to prevent and contain it and the ensuing impunity must be addressed as part of the struggle to eliminate all forms of GBV. [13] proposes that to curb online GBV, there should be public awareness of the GBV issue. The success of the online GBV campaign as digital activism also depends on public participation in the issues being fought for in this movement. The [30] suggests that social media is useful for raising awareness. In this regard, [6] encourage interventions such as campaigns to use social media algorithms to send targeted messages aimed at preventing GBV and promoting gender equality.

The measures taken against the perpetrators should not exacerbate violence by taking a punitive approach and using violence against violence [31]. [32] suggests that laws be promulgated on the content of social media. Similarly, [8] contends that governments also have a responsibility to create better laws to protect women from targeted harassment online and even the playing field for everyone. [9] also highlights that as the internet and digital technology become increasingly integrated into people's lives, robust policies are required to curb exposure to online violence.

The study conducted by [33] encourages the Ministry of Communications, together with the Portfolio Committee on Communications in the Parliament of the Republic of South Africa, to rapidly implement measures that could help to prevent social media users, especially youth, from doing things that result in social disharmony when they are online.

Further, [33] highlights that social media education can be used as another tool to combat online criminal activities such as GBV. [16] believes that human rights activists, organizations and political leaders should condemn GBV through various platforms, including the media. Civil society in South Africa has organized and mobilized marches and protests, tirelessly speaking out against the issue of violence against women in the country. [34] also suggests that government leaders and gender activists should be fervent allies to prevent GBV in South Africa.

According to [6], the government should run online campaigns to dispel misconceptions about GBV. Similarly, [35] encourages a collaborative approach between the government, social media users and health professionals to curb GBV. According to [8], the easiest way to prevent online GBV is for victims to retreat from and leave online spaces, but this then infringes their right to express and access information. In terms of how targets of online GBV respond to this scourge, most LGBTIQ youth resort to measures such as blocking, deleting offensive content and adjusting privacy settings to cope with cyber victimization [16].

[36] explains that feminist online activism could help to prevent online GBV because there is considerable success in building networks that critique and disrupt dominant discourses, construct counter narratives, connect conversations around specific events to broader feminist issues and reiterate the value of discourse and narrative in public forums and their potential for enacting structural change.

According to [37], gender inequality perpetuates cultures of violence, particularly GBV. The author explains that in gender-unequal societies, women are seen as less important than men, or as men's possessions, meaning that men feel a little hesitation in abusing women, and believe that their satisfaction is more important than women's. Similarly, gender-unequal societies tend to allow women little agency in controlling their sexual interactions.

The study by [38] reveals that engagement on social media is good when women are engaging with people who have the same views as theirs. In addition, women positioning themselves as not being angry about GBV by themselves find comfort and gain allies.

1. 3. Suggested solutions to the problem

In South Africa, online GBV is a disturbing issue. Thus, the described problem of online GBV can be solved if the proposed solutions are considered by individuals, civil society, and

government practitioners. The following measures can be used to avoid and prevent online GBV in South Africa:

- outreach programmes, public awareness and social media campaigns could help to mitigate or prevent online GBV in South Africa;
- combining social media campaigns with in-person interventions delivers promising results;
- social media owners should intervene and immediately take firm action to fight online GBV in South Africa. This could be done by including moderating comments, publicly condemning perpetrators, reporting them to authorities, or banning such users;
- measures taken against the perpetrator should not exacerbate violence;
- governments have a responsibility to create better social media laws to protect women from targeted harassment online. Social media users, lawmakers and civil society must address online GBV;
- social media education can be used to combat online criminal activities such as GBV;
- human rights activists, organizations and political leaders should condemn online GBV;
- victims should retreat from online spaces to prevent online GBV;
- feminist online activism could help to prevent online GBV;
- to avoid the continuous effects of online GBV, the South African government should launch online and in-person campaigns to end the rise in online GBV;
- women need to launch campaigns that will focus on allowing them to voice their concerns and make their voices heard on various social media platforms;
- the South African government should establish more policy frameworks to protect women and members of the LGBTQ+ community from targeted harassment online;
- the South African government should update existing legal and policy frameworks, e.g. the Cybercrimes Act, to elaborate on and further develop a comprehensive definition of what constitutes online GBV;
- social media developers in partnership with South African government entities such as GCIS should launch social media education programmes as well as social behavior change programmes to combat online GBV;
- South Africans who are social media users should be advised to exit inappropriate social media platforms, particularly those that trap and lead them to online GBV;
- social media researchers should research to identify additional solutions to issues affecting online GBV in South Africa;
- civil leaders and the private sector should take action as part of the fight against gender equality;
- *issues of online GBV should be given preference during the 16 days of activism against GBV from 25 November to 10 December;*
- social media developers and internet intermediaries should consider funding online safety training for different social media platforms to curb online GBV;
- civil society should empower women and girls with digital safety tools;
- social welfare services are urgently needed to protect children and women against abuse and consequences of livelihood, health and social insurance to help secure services in times of need, which may be subsidized, with potential contribution payment exemptions for the poor.

2. Materials and Methods

This study fell within the broader scope of the qualitative approach, which [39] is defined as an approach that aims to interpret how individuals experience and understand the social world within their social context. Thus, a systematic review was carried out to explore social media as a campaign tool against online GBV in South Africa. [40] describe a systematic review as a comprehensive and systematic search to locate all relevant published work that addresses one or more research questions, followed by a systematic presentation and integration of the characteristics and findings of that search. A systematic review delivered a meticulous summary of all the available primary research in response to a research question on this study.

Data for the study was extracted by using scientific search engines for articles, as well as books. Computer-based scientific search engines such as Google Scholar, Google, EbscoHost, ResearchGate, ScienceDirect and Scopus were assessed to extract relevant data from July 2022 to November 2022. Articles were assessed, based on the formulated inclusion criteria and their relevance. Furthermore, for the researchers to select relevant articles, purposive sampling was employed. The keywords of this study were used to extract relevant data sources.

The following criteria were used to select articles for inclusion and exclusion in this research guided by purposive sampling:

- Articles on social media as a campaign tool against online GBV in South Africa;
- Studies that reported on social media as a campaign tool against online GBV across the globe;
- Primary studies that showed originality in the field of the research;
- Studies were conducted between mainly 2002 and 2022.

Fig. 1 below shows the process that was followed in selecting the articles for inclusion in this study. In total, the initial search revealed 100 records, and an additional 8 records (books) and other unpublished literature were consulted, giving a total of 108 records. From this total, 30 records were removed, either as a result of a duplication of information or because they had not met the inclusion criteria. The remaining numbers of records were 78, from which 60 were further screened. After screening, 11 records were excluded because they contained irrelevant information. The remaining 49 records were then assessed for eligibility. A further 5 articles were excluded because they contained information about other countries. Finally, only 36 articles and 8 books, i.e. a total of 44, were used for this study.

In the process of assessing the studies to be included in this systematic review, the researchers took the following five steps:

- framing the question for review;
- identifying relevant work for the study;
- assessing the quality of the studies;
- summarising the evidence;
- interpreting the findings.

Fig. 1. Process followed in identifying articles relevant to this study (PRISMA)

The researchers used the thematic analysis method to analyze data gathered from the repository about social media as a campaign tool against online GBV in South Africa.

The reason for adopting thematic analysis was that the researchers wanted to deal with patterns which would allow thick analysis that was more understandable and to explore how social media incites GBV and what can be done to prevent online GBV. According to [41], thematic analysis underpins most qualitative research analysis, whether or not it is explicitly stated. Additionally, it draws on the organization of data into relevant themes, which are the broad codes assigned to the main issues arising in data (usually justified in terms of the frequency with which they occur).

For this study, the researchers organized data in different themes and sub-themes that had emerged in a narrative revised form. The thematic coding in the study helped to categorize and explore how social media could be used as a campaign tool against online GBV in South Africa. All themes were crafted following the objectives of the study which were to assess how South Africans use social media platforms, identify the root causes of online GBV in South Africa and propose intervention strategies to combat online GBV in South Africa.

3. Results

The results of the study are based on themes and sub-themes developed by the researchers.

Usage of social media platforms by South Africans.

This finding focuses on the usage of various social media platforms by South Africans:

- South Africans use social media platforms to influence public opinion. It was found that social media platforms such as Twitter are powerful platforms for public opinion among South Africans;

- South Africans use social media for mobilizing the public and building solidarity;

- South Africans use social media for communication purposes;

- for South Africans, social media platforms are used as a common venue for harassment and online GBV. This result clearly shows that South Africans use social media for good and immoral reasons;

- South Africans also use social media to rally against online GBV.

Root causes of online GBV in South Africa.

This finding exposes the root causes of online GBV in South Africa. The research has shown that online GBV can have extensive negative impacts on women and the LGBTIQ community:

- patriarchy encourages the notion of control over women's lives and is embedded in society's norms and values;

- lack of support for the victims/survivors of online violence against women causes GBV to spread;

- there is a lack of access to other kinds of public spaces for the exchange of information;

- some social media do not require the verification of users on signup. This allows some social media perpetrators to commit online GBV;

- lack of public awareness of the GBV issue provokes virtual violence among South Africans;

- some social networking site users in South Africa are not aware of what exactly can be considered harassment or illegal activity and this makes it difficult to prevent online GBV;

- connection or relationship between the victim/survivor and the perpetrator may lead to online GBV.

Accessing, using, manipulating and/or disseminating private data without consent incites online GBV.

4. Discussion

The results above are relevant to many existing literature in South Africa and across the world. By utilizing a punitive strategy and using violence against violence, the actions taken against the offenders should not make the situation of violence worse. [31, 32] proposes passing legislation governing social media content. Similar to this, [8] argues that governments also

have a duty to provide better legal frameworks to shield women from specific internet harassment and level the playing field. [9] further emphasizes the need for strong rules to reduce exposure to online violence as people's lives increasingly incorporate the internet and digital technology.

[33] also emphasizes the use of social media education as a further instrument in the fight against online criminal activities like GBV. [16] think that GBV should be denounced by human rights advocates, organizations, and political figures on a variety of forums, including the media. South Africa's civil society has tirelessly spoken out against the issue of violence against women there by planning and mobilizing marches and protests. [34] adds that in order to stop GBV in South Africa, political leaders and gender activists need work closely together.

Limitations of the study and future research directions.

The study's limitations include the fact that the findings from the sources consulted from various repositories should not be generalized without caution. Online GBV was discovered to be a sensitive issue that must be dealt with by social media users, government, private sectors, social media developers and civil leaders, among others, but empirical research studies could provide more insight into this topic as online GBV is affecting the lives of many South Africans. This study's data was only extracted by using scientific search engines for articles, which may not be sufficient to address the in-depth knowledge required for the online GBV topic. Future research should look into the long-term online GBV implications on South African social media users, given the critical need to prevent this continuous online behavior.

5. Conclusion

This study explored what GBV is and some of the forms it takes examined GBV challenges in South Africa and lastly proposed intervention strategies to combat online GBV in South Africa. Based on the results of the study, it may be concluded that online GBV is very frequent nowadays in South Africa. It was also established in this study that patriarchy, lack of support for the victims/survivors of online violence against women, lack of access to other kinds of public spaces for the exchange of information and organizing and lack of public awareness of the GBV issue are among the causes of online GBV in South Africa. Unfortunately, most South Africans do not have enough knowledge to recognize and react in an appropriate way against online GBV.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author and other co-authors. The data are not publicly available due to restrictions.

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